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Trim31 is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.

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We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery of *Trim31* as a zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

Citations

1. Zhang, K., Liu, D., Li, Y., Shi, Z., Guo, J., Gao, C., Wang, H., Ju, Z. and Diao, D., 2023. The E3 ligase TRIM31 regulates hematopoietic stem cell homeostasis and MLL-AF9 leukemia. *Haematologica*, 108(8), p.2116.